

SIVIM Deciduous Forests – Database of deciduous forests from the Iberian Peninsula

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Abstract

“SIVIM Deciduous Forests” is a thematic database established in 2015, focused on forest vegetation from the Iberian Peninsula and southern France. It was registered in the Global Index of Vegetation Databases (GIVD ID: EU-00-023) in January 2016. All types of temperate and submediterranean non-riparian deciduous forests of the phytosociological classes *Carpino-Fagetea sylvaticae*, *Quercetea pubescentis* and *Quercetea robori-petraeae* (formerly combined in the class *Quercu-Fagetea*) are represented in the database. Currently, it contains 6,642 published vegetation plots of beech, birch, ash, lime and other deciduous mixed forests, as well as forests dominated by different species of deciduous and marcescent oaks, 100% of them classified at association level. Data are stored in TURBOVEG format, and are available upon request from the international vegetation-plot databases EVA and sPlot in semi-restricted regime. The relevés have also been included in SIVIM database, and thus they are freely available online. However, in SIVIM Deciduous Forests geolocation accuracy has been improved and the taxonomy and syntaxonomy unified. Plot size is available for 73% of the relevés, of which 82% are between 100 and 400 m². Plant taxonomy is standardized to Flora iberica. During the last four years, data of SIVIM Deciduous Forests were requested via EVA and sPlot for different projects, and have been used for several studies with various objectives, from floristic, vegetation and habitat-related topics to macroecological studies, and from local to global scales.

Abbreviations: EVA = European Vegetation Archive; GIVD = Global Index of Vegetation-Plot Databases; SIVIM = Iberian and Macaronesian Vegetation Information System.

Keywords

Deciduous forest, Iberian Peninsula, Pyrenees, *Quercu-Fagetea*, relevé, secondary forest, submediterranean forest, temperate forest, vegetation-plot database

GIVD Fact Sheet

GIVD Database ID: EU-00-023		Last update: 2020-12-07	
SIVIM Deciduous Forests		Web address:	
Database manager(s): Juan Antonio Campos (juanan.campos@ehu.eus)			
Owner: Juan Antonio Campos, Arnau Mercadé & Xavier Font			
Scope: Phytosociological relevés of deciduous forest (<i>Carpino-Fagetea sylvaticae</i> , <i>Quercetea pubescentis</i> and <i>Quercetea robori-petraeae</i> classes) in the Iberian Peninsula and southern France.			
Abstract:			
Availability: according to a specific agreement		Online upload: no	Online search: no
Database format(s): TURBOVEG		Export format(s): TURBOVEG, MS Access, Excel	
Plot type(s): normal plots		Plot-size range: 1 to 3000 m ²	
Non-overlapping plots: 6642	Estimate of existing plots: 7000	Completeness: 100%	Status: completed and continuing
Total no. of plot observations: 6642	Number of sources (biblioreferences, data collectors): 308	Valid taxa: 2647	
Countries (%): Spain: 71; France: 22; Portugal: 1.9; Andorra: 0.42			
Formations: Forest: 100%. Terrestrial: 100%			
Guilds: all vascular plants: 100%			
Environmental data (%): altitude: 98; slope aspect: 73; slope inclination: 68			
Performance measure(s): cover: 100%			
Geographic localisation: GPS coordinates (precision 25 m or less): 0%; point coordinates less precise than GPS, up to 1 km: 42.7%; small grid (not coarser than 10 km): 52.3%; political units or only on a coarser scale (above 10 km): 5%			
Sampling periods: before 1920: 0%; 1920-1929: 0%; 1930-1939: 0.34%; 1940-1949: 1%; 1950-1959: 2.5%; 1960-1969: 6.2%; 1970-1979: 8.3%; 1980-1989: 35.2%; 1990-1999: 29.16%; 2000-2009: 14%; 2010-2019: 3.3%; unknown: 0%			
Information as of 2020-12-07 further details and future updates available from http://www.givd.info/ID/EU-00-023			

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